

Study on Throughputs in 5G and Beyond Networks

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Abstract—This article provides an analysis of throughput in modern 5G networks, a topic of ongoing importance as research efforts shift toward defining 6G performance requirements. First, the influence of 5G New Radio network configuration parameters on throughput is examined based on technical specifications from the latest 3GPP Release 18. Next, real-world factors reducing the default theoretical data rates between base stations and user equipment are analyzed. Following this, network-scale factors affecting throughput are considered. Finally, assumptions regarding throughput performance in beyond-5G networks are proposed. The study shows that while theoretical data rates in 5G can be high, practical constraints often lead to significant performance gaps—highlighting areas for improvement in future network generations.

Keywords—throughput, 5G, 6G, IMT-2020, IMT-2030, data rates, spectral efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

Significant efforts are currently being directed towards envisioning the architecture of 6G networks. The 5G specifications have reached a mature stage, with 3GPP’s 5G-Advanced Release 19 expected to be finalized in 2025. The upcoming Release 20 is anticipated to serve as a transition towards 6G and includes active studies in that direction. Release 21, expected around 2029–2030, will be the first full 6G release aligned with the ITU’s IMT-2030 framework and requirements [1].

Numerous research and engineering groups are investigating various aspects of the future 6G network architecture. Among these, the EWOC project explores the coexistence of optical and wireless technologies in beyond-5G networks. In particular, the authors of [2] highlight that due to the increasing convergence between optical and wireless network components, different resource management strategies across network layers must therefore converge and collaborate closely to achieve future network performance targets. This growing convergence makes it crucial even for optical researchers, such as those working on fronthaul transport optimization, to understand the air interface behavior. The air interface serves as the primary connection point for user equipment (UE) and significantly influences all subsequent network processes because it originates network traffic.

To explore the potential evolution of throughput requirements for beyond-5G networks, this paper reviews recent 5G Release 18 documents and ITU standards to establish theoretical limits (Section II). It then assesses practical factors limiting real-world throughput at the individual base station (BS) to UE connection scale (Section III) and examines throughput from a broader network perspective (Section IV). Finally, assumptions about potential data rate enhancements in beyond-5G networks are proposed (Section V).

II. SINGLE-LINK MAXIMUM THEORETICAL THROUGHPUT

The maximum theoretical throughput in OFDM-based systems depends on several fundamental parameters: 1 — frequency bandwidth (BW) and subcarrier spacing (SCS) determine the number of subcarriers available for

transmission at any given moment; 2 — the duration of one OFDM symbol defines how many symbols can be transmitted per unit of time; 3 — multiplying the number of subcarriers by the number of OFDM symbols gives the total number of OFDM cells, each of which can be modulated with a different scheme carrying a specific number of bits per cell; 4 — if the system has more than one antenna, it can employ different multiple antenna techniques, such as parallel spatial streams, beamforming, or sector antennas, to reuse space, adding extra layers to the OFDM grid within the same time and frequency.

A simple multiplication of the above terms provides the total number of bits available over the air (at the physical layer) in any OFDM-based radio interface technology and can be visualized as Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Visual interpretation of OFDM grid information capacity.

5G networks can operate in a wide range of configurations that affect throughput. The maximum theoretical user data throughput between one BS and one UE in 5G NR radio interface can be calculated using the formula adapted from Section 4.1 of [3]:

$$T = (N_{RB} \cdot 12) \cdot \frac{N_{sym} \cdot 2^\mu}{10^{-3}} \cdot N_{mod} \cdot CR \cdot N_{MIMO} \cdot N_C \cdot (1 - OH) \quad (1)$$

The term $(N_{RB} \cdot 12)$ represents the number of available frequency subcarriers, determined not directly by the channel BW, but by the number of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) within a channel, denoted as N_{RB} . Each PRB contains 12 subcarriers, but SCS differs depending on radio frame configuration, resulting in different PRB BWs. 5G employs a flexible radio frame structure to accommodate varying channel conditions across a wide frequency range and different channel BWs. Instead of using fixed parameters, different OFDM configurations are supported through the concept of numerology. The complete mapping of 5G NR frequency ranges (FRs), channel BWs, SCS and N_{RB} can be found in Section 5.3 of [4]. Different network configurations exhibit variations in spectral efficiency. In Table I, BW utilization efficiency is calculated for all possible 5G network configurations based on the ratio between PRB BWs, channel BWs, and the required frequency guard bands for OFDM signal.

TABLE I. CHANNEL BANDWIDTH UTILIZATION % IN DIFFERENT 5G CHANNEL CONFIGURATIONS

BW, MHz	3	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	60	70	80	90	100	200	400	800	1600	2000	
Subcarrier spacing, kHz	Bandwidth utilization efficiency in FR1 channels (410 – 7 125 MHz), %																					
	15	90.0	90.0	93.6	94.8	95.4	95.8	96.0	96.7	97.2	96.8	97.2										
	30		79.2	86.4	91.2	91.8	93.6	93.6	94.6	95.4	95.2	95.8	97.2	97.2	97.7	98.0	98.3					
	60			79.2	86.4	86.4	89.3	91.2	90.5	91.8	92.8	93.6	94.8	95.7	96.3	96.8	97.2					
	Bandwidth utilization efficiency in FR2-1 channels (24 250 – 52 600 MHz), %																					
	60											95.0					95.0	95.0				
	120											92.2					95.0	95.0	95.0			
	Bandwidth utilization efficiency in FR2-2 channels (52 600 – 71 000 MHz), %																					
	120																95.0		95.0			
	480																	95.0	89.3	89.3		
960																	95.0	89.3	89.3	85.2		

As can be seen from the table, the best spectral efficiency is achieved for the 100 MHz channel in FR1 with 30 kHz SCS: in this case, 98.3% of channel BW is occupied by subcarriers. In contrast, the widest 2 GHz channel configuration reaches only 85.2% utilization, effectively losing nearly 300 MHz.

The term $\frac{N_{\text{sym}} \cdot 2^\mu}{10^{-3}}$ represents the number of OFDM symbols transmitted per second. Since numerology affects both SCS and symbol duration, the total number of symbols per unit time depends on the numerology index μ . The value of N_{sym} can be either 12 or 14 symbols (in most cases) per slot, depending on the OFDM cyclic prefix configuration.

The modulation order is denoted by N_{mod} . It corresponds to one of the following utilized modulation schemes: QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM, 256-QAM, or 1024-QAM, which carry 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 bits per modulation symbol, respectively.

Depending on the channel conditions, different coding rates (CR) can be selected to ensure reliable transmission. For the calculation of maximum theoretical throughput, the highest possible coding rate is considered, given by $CR_{\text{max}} = 948/1024$. Due to coding, the number of user data bits transmitted over the air is reduced proportionally to the coding rate. Combined with the modulation scheme, the coding rate defines the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), which can be selected and adapted dynamically based on current channel conditions (Sections 5.1.3 and 6.1.4 of [5]).

The number of available spatial layers for transmission—known as Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) layers and denoted as N_{MIMO} —depends on the capabilities of both the BS and the UE. Current 3GPP specifications support up to 8 spatial layers in the downlink (DL) and 4 in the uplink (UL) direction.

5G supports transmission with BWs wider than the maximum channel BW through carrier aggregation, where the BS and UE combine multiple component carriers to boost data rates (e.g., 100 + 100 MHz in FR1). The parameter N_C accounts for the number of aggregated carriers in the throughput calculation.

Not all cells in the OFDM grid are used for user data transmission; a portion is reserved for control functions. The final term in the formula accounts for this overhead, which depends on network configuration and can be precisely calculated only for a specific setup. For general throughput estimations, [3] provides average overhead values, which range from 8% to 18%.

Throughput is calculated by (1) under the assumption that all available resources are used in one direction, corresponding to Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD), where DL and UL operate on separate frequencies. FDD remains in use today, particularly for low-band frequencies in FR1. For higher frequency bands in FR1, and for all bands in FR2, Time Division Duplexing (TDD) is employed. In TDD mode, slots are flexibly allocated between DL and UL. A typical 5G configuration uses a DL-to-UL ratio of about 4:1, reflecting current traffic patterns where DL traffic exceeds UL traffic by roughly 10:1. Since spectral efficiency in the uplink is often more than twice as low in practice, the 4:1 TDD format addresses this asymmetry in data flows. A minor drawback of TDD compared to FDD is the need for a guard interval when switching from DL to UL (but not from UL to DL), slightly reducing time utilization efficiency (at least one OFDM symbol).

To illustrate throughput values for different network configurations, Table II presents calculations for a single channel using the maximum available BW in each FR. The calculated results can be compared with the IMT-2020 requirements, established by the ITU as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for 5G communication systems. According to ITU-R Report [6], the requirements for a BS transmitting to a UE under ideal conditions include peak data rates of 20 Gbps (DL) and 10 Gbps (UL), and spectral efficiency targets of 30 b/s/Hz (DL) and 15 b/s/Hz (UL).

Analysis of the Table II calculations shows that, under ideal conditions and using a single spatial layer, the system achieves a spectral efficiency of approximately 5.5–7 b/s/Hz across all frequency ranges. When these values are multiplied by the maximum available BW in each FR, the resulting peak data rates fall significantly short of the IMT-2020 targets: 8.97 Gbps instead of 20 Gbps and 2.42 Gbps instead of 10 Gbps in the best case of FR2-2.

The main spectral efficiency boost factor in 5G is the use of multi-antenna systems. The spectral efficiency evaluation guidelines in [6] assume that the 5G system is capable of using 8×8 MIMO in the DL and 4×4 MIMO in the UL. When the spectral efficiency values are scaled by the corresponding number of spatial layers, the required spectral efficiency targets are exceeded in all cases. However, even with such high spectral efficiency, the available channel BWs are still insufficient to meet the peak data rate requirements in FR1 and FR2-1. Consequently, achieving the IMT-2020-defined peak bitrates for a single UE typically requires carrier aggregation in most scenarios.

TABLE II. NETWORK CONFIGURATIONS THROUGHPUT COMPARISON

Parameter	1 st Network configuration	2 nd Network configuration	3 rd Network configuration
Frequency range (GHz)	FR1 (0.41–7.125)	FR2-1 (24.25–52.6)	FR2-2 (52.6–71.0)
NR operating Band (GHz)	n78 (3.3–3.8)	n257 (26.5–29.5)	n263 (57–71)
Transmission BW, MHz	100	400	2 000
Subcarrier spacing, kHz	30	120	960
Number of PRBs	273	264	148
Modulation	QAM1024 DL, QAM256 UL		
Code rate	948/1024		
OFDM symbols / second	28 000	112 000	896 000
OFDM cells / second	7 644 000	29 568 000	132 608 000
TDD slot configuration	DDD-F(d10f2u2)-U (52 DL, 2 guard band, 16 UL symbols), DL/UL ratio \approx 74%/23%		
Overhead	0.14 DL 0.08 UL	0.18 DL 0.10 UL	
Peak throughput per one spatial layer, Gbps	0.54 DL 0.14 UL	2.00 DL 0.54 UL	8.97 DL 2.42 UL
Peak spectral efficiency per one spatial layer, b/s/Hz	6.78 DL 7.14 UL	6.25 DL 6.76 UL	5.61 DL 6.06 UL
MIMO configuration	8x8 DL, 4x4 UL		
Peak throughput per one cell DL/UL, Gbps	4.34 DL 0.57 UL	16.01 DL 2.16 UL	71.79 DL 9.70 UL
Peak spectral efficiency per one cell, b/s/Hz	54.25 DL 28.57 UL	50.02 DL 27.03 UL	44.87 DL 24.24 UL

III. SINGLE-LINK PRACTICALLY ACHIEVABLE THROUGHPUT

Throughput in real-world scenarios is always lower than the theoretical maximum due to non-ideal radio conditions. Link adaptation algorithms at the BS adjust transmission parameters every transmission time interval (TTI), the basic scheduling unit in the OFDM grid. In 5G, TTI duration is fixed but scales with numerology, from 1 ms downward. Thus, real-world throughput over a 1-second BS–UE link averages across 1000 TTIs (for 1 ms TTIs), each with potentially different throughput. The primary factors contributing to throughput degradation in the BS–UE link include:

1) MIMO conditions. Based on the estimated channel quality, the BS determines the number of spatial streams, known as the MIMO rank (e.g., 1, 2, ..., 8), for each scheduled TTI. This rank may be lower than the theoretical maximum even if both BS and UE support higher MIMO configurations. For instance, if both ends support 4x4 MIMO, the spatial channel conditions might allow only 2x2 in practice. This results in a proportional reduction in throughput for that TTI. As a result, the average MIMO rank over a 1-second interval may fall below the maximum, such as 3.6 instead of 4.

2) Achievable MCS. Similar to MIMO, the BS dynamically selects the appropriate MCS index per TTI. The maximum throughput formula assumes the use of 1024-QAM with a coding rate of 948/1024, achieving a spectral efficiency of 9.2578 b/s/Hz (Table 5.1.3.1-4 in [5]). However, this level is possible only under ideal conditions, such as when the UE is close to the BS. In practice, as path loss increases with distance, the BS selects a lower MCS index. MCS tables include a wide range of spectral efficiency values down to QPSK with a coding rate of 30/1024, corresponding to a

spectral efficiency of 0.0586 b/s/Hz (Table 5.1.3.1-3 in [5]). This implies a possible degradation by a factor of \sim 158 (i.e., $9.2578 / 0.0586$) between ideal and worst-case conditions. In such cases, most bits transmitted are for error correction rather than user data. Furthermore, the MCS index table supporting 1024-QAM was only introduced in [5] in December 2021. As of today, 1024-QAM is not widely deployed in commercial networks, and most BSs still support only up to 256-QAM with a maximum spectral efficiency of 7.4063 b/s/Hz in the DL. In the UL, performance is further limited by lower UE transmission power, difficulties in antenna implementation in compact devices, and overall hardware limitations. As a result, UL modulation order typically does not exceed 64-QAM, with a maximum practical spectral efficiency of 5.5547 b/s/Hz (Section 6.1.4 of [5]).

3) Retransmission loss. Throughput is also reduced by retransmission mechanisms in 5G, namely Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) at the MAC layer and Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) at the RLC layer. If a code block is not correctly decoded by the receiver, the BS schedules a retransmission. Typically, retransmission mechanisms are designed to maintain a block error rate (BLER) of approximately 10%, as BLER serves as a target parameter in link adaptation algorithms. These retransmissions work together with channel coding to ensure reliable data delivery. For example, under deteriorating channel conditions, the system may continue using the same MCS until the BLER exceeds 10%. Once this threshold is reached, the scheduler lowers the MCS index to maintain the target reliability. Thus, even in stable environments, retransmissions can cause up to a 10% throughput loss, and more under poor conditions.

Fig. 2 shows the impact of MCS adaptation and retransmissions in a real network, based on a recording from a UE connected to the Tampere University 5G test network. The UE continuously performed a looped speed test sequence: ping–DL–UL. The fragment shows four distinct DL test periods, where the MCS index (blue line) stays near the maximum value (index 27, dashed line) during the first DL test, with almost no DL retransmissions (blue bars). As the UE moves and radio conditions worsen, the MCS decreases to keep the DL BLER below 10%. In the UL, conditions are consistently poorer: retransmissions during UL tests reach about 10%, and the MCS stays below index 15. During ping and DL phases, when UL transmissions are limited to small control packets, the UL MCS temporarily increases. The behavior observed in Fig. 2 results in a reduction of the actual throughput averaged over time.

Fig. 2. Illustration of MCS and retransmission losses behavior in real-world channel conditions.

The reduction in throughput compared to the theoretical maximum can be expressed by the following formula:

$$T_{\text{real}} = T_{\text{max}} \cdot (1 - L_{\text{retr}}) \cdot \frac{MIMO_{\text{real}}}{MIMO_{\text{max}}} \cdot \frac{MCS_{\text{real SE}}}{MCS_{\text{max SE}}} \quad (2)$$

where T_{max} is the theoretical maximum throughput calculated by (1), L_{retr} is the retransmission loss coefficient, and the two ratios reflect the difference between theoretical and actually achieved MIMO ranks and spectral efficiency.

MIMO ranks, MCS indices, and retransmission losses for each TTI are functions of channel conditions. Consequently, predicting practically achievable throughput requires BS–UE link-level simulations using specified channel models. Additionally, as can be inferred from Fig. 2, these factors also depend on algorithm implementations. Since 3GPP does not specify particular implementations, BS efficiency in adapting to channel conditions differs across vendor solutions.

To reflect real-world conditions, the IMT-2020 framework defines not only peak data rates but also KPIs for 'user experienced' data rates — minimum guaranteed throughputs for a single user. According to [6], the target for 5G is at least 100 Mbps DL and 50 Mbps UL. While it is fundamentally impossible to guarantee a specific speed in a mobile network, there is a quasi-assurance based on a high likelihood of achieving a defined data rate in practice. User experienced throughput is defined as the 5th percentile of the cumulative distribution function of user throughput—i.e., 95% of users should experience throughput equal to or greater than this value. Therefore, the ITU's expectation for minimum to maximum user throughputs in 5G spans a 200-fold range: 100 Mbps - 20 Gbps DL and 50 Mbps - 10 Gbps UL.

Regarding spectral efficiency targets, in addition to peak values (30 b/s/Hz DL and 15 b/s/Hz UL), [6] also defines minimum (0.225 b/s/Hz DL and 0.15 b/s/Hz UL) and average (7.8 b/s/Hz DL and 5.4 b/s/Hz UL) values (for the Dense Urban deployment scenario; details in the next section). Minimum spectral efficiency is defined in the same way as the 5th percentile of user spectral efficiency. These requirements allow assessing the gap between expected real-world values and the calculated maximum.

IV. NETWORK-SCALE THROUGHPUTS

The previous sections considered a single BS–UE link. In real deployments, multiple users are served simultaneously by one BS and move between BSs across the network. Real-world network topologies, of course, can vary in many ways. 3GPP and ITU define standardized deployment scenarios that reflect typical real-world cases [7], [8]. These scenarios specify key network parameters such as cell radius, cell density, user behavior, and more, forming the basis for network-scale throughput analysis.

In this section, we focus on the scenario that addresses both continuous coverage and high traffic loads — the Dense Urban scenario, whose network layout is illustrated in Fig. 3. It is a heterogeneous deployment scenario with two layers. The macro layer follows a traditional cellular network layout based on a regular hexagonal grid with an inter-site distance (ISD) of 200 meters, with antennas placed above rooftop level. It operates around 4 GHz with a channel BW of up to 200 MHz. The micro layer includes three micro sites randomly distributed within each macro cell, featuring outdoor antennas below rooftop level and operating at approximately 30 GHz with up to 1 GHz BW.

Fig. 3. Dense Urban deployment scenario layout.

In practical deployments, macro sites typically use three-sector antennas, each covering 120 degrees, instead of a single omnidirectional antenna. This setup creates three sectors (or cells) per site, tripling throughput over the same area. The Dense Urban scenario assumes three-sector antennas for the macro layer and omnidirectional antennas for the micro layer.

Modern mobile networks use a frequency reuse factor of one, meaning all BSs operate on the same frequency. As a result, macro layers, especially with short ISD like in Dense Urban deployments, become interference-limited rather than noise-limited. At cell edges (mid-ISD), signals from adjacent BSs have similar strength, degrading the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR). In these conditions, interference dominates, while noise remains far lower due to high transmission powers and short distances. In Section II, throughput calculations assumed MCS selection was primarily a function of path loss under noise-limited conditions. However, in a full-network context, SINR is often constrained by interference, particularly at cell edges. As shown in Section III, this can reduce the MCS index to its lowest possible values. As a result, a significant portion of theoretical throughput is lost due to inter-cell interference (ICI) in today's networks. Conversely, micro sites are typically noise-limited, due to lower transmit powers, higher path loss at high frequencies, and below-rooftop antenna placements, leading to more localized, discontinuous coverage.

Another important but hard-to-measure factor for modeling is user behavior, including user distribution, mobility patterns, and traffic characteristics. User distribution within the cell is critical. For example, a cell with ten stationary users near the BS may achieve throughput close to the theoretical maximum, while twenty users moving near the cell edges will generate data that mainly consists of error correction bits and retransmissions, with lower MIMO ranks and MCS indices, reducing overall throughput. The Dense Urban scenario assumes 10 users per macro cell (30 per macro site with 3 sectors), randomly distributed. Each micro site also serves 10 users clustered within its coverage area. According to the model, 80% of users are indoors moving at 3 km/h, and 20% are outdoors, typically in vehicles moving at 80 km/h. The baseline traffic model assumes full-buffer conditions, with each UE continuously demanding transmission resources.

Network-level throughput is assessed through system-level simulations based on the scenario parameters. The general simulation process includes the following steps: 1 — deployment of the network layout according to the scenario specifications; 2 — user distribution across the simulation area; 3 — association of each UE to a serving BS, typically

the geographically nearest BS under a basic cell selection rule; 4 — definition of a traffic model; 5 — link-level simulation for each BS–UE pair, applying a suitable channel model defined in [8]; 6 — radio resource scheduling, where each BS allocates OFDM symbols to UEs based on instantaneous channel conditions and scheduling algorithms; 7 — calculation of the total network throughput by aggregating the throughput of all active links. These simulation steps are repeated over the duration of the scenario, updating UE positions at each time step according to the mobility model.

At the final stage, overall network performance can be evaluated by calculating the area traffic capacity, defined as the total throughput per unit area (in b/s/m²). For a deployment with a single macro layer, the area of one site (one hexagon) can be expressed as $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} ISD^2$, and the area traffic capacity can be calculated as:

$$T_{\text{area}} = \frac{2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{cells}}} T_i}{\sqrt{3} \cdot ISD^2 \cdot N_{\text{sites}}} \quad (3)$$

where T_i is the throughput of cell i , and N_{cells} and N_{sites} are the total number of cells and sites in the area under consideration.

In heterogeneous deployments like the Dense Urban scenario, the micro layer throughput is calculated separately and added to the macro layer. While micro cells do not provide continuous coverage, they are deployed to compensate for coverage gaps in high-mobility environments and enhance the consistency of area traffic capacity.

Initially, the IMT-2020 framework defined area traffic capacity only for one scenario—Indoor Hotspot—with a target of 10 Mbit/s/m². This value, equivalent to 10 Tbit/s/km², is clearly unrealistic for macro layer deployments whose primary function is to provide broad coverage rather than extreme capacity. Later, 3GPP introduced service requirements for other deployment scenarios in [9], including area traffic capacity targets. For the Dense Urban case, the targets are 750 Gbit/s/km² (DL) and 125 Gbit/s/km² (UL), assuming 25,000 users with 10% of them simultaneously active.

Of course, the outlined simulation methodologies cannot fully capture real-world conditions. For example, the full-buffer traffic model assumes constant user demand and reflects best-case scheduler performance, while actual traffic is bursty and diverse, affecting scheduling efficiency. Similarly, the assumption of uniformly distributed users does not match real-world patterns, and site locations do not follow a perfect hexagonal grid. Despite these limitations, system-level simulations provide reasonably accurate estimates of network throughput capacity and useful insights into expected performance. Transport network’s capacity—particularly the fronthaul and midhaul segments—can be approximated from the area traffic capacity and the overall network topology. In this study, throughput refers to layer-3 user-plane data, corresponding to functional split option 1 in centralized RAN architectures. As such, these results can serve as a baseline for evaluating transport requirements under higher functional split options.

V. ASSUMPTIONS ON BEYOND 5G NETWORK DATA RATES

In November 2023, the ITU published the framework and high-level objectives for the development of sixth-generation networks, referred to as IMT-2030 [1]. However, detailed KPIs such as target throughput and spectral efficiency—

similar to those established for IMT-2020—are still under evaluation. Recommendation [1] provides preliminary values as research targets: 50/100/200 Gbps peak data rate, 300/500 Mbps user-experienced rate; spectral efficiency targets are 1.5 and 3 times greater than IMT-2020; and area traffic capacity values are 30 Mbit/s/m² and 50 Mbit/s/m². At this early stage, before the requirements are fully established, several key factors can be identified that are likely to significantly influence the achievable throughput and spectral efficiency in beyond-5G systems:

A. Spectrum expansion

Higher data rates are expected primarily through extensive spectrum expansion. As discussed in Section II, spectral efficiency per spatial layer remains relatively constant across all frequency ranges; current higher rates are mainly due to wider channel BWs. Moving beyond the existing 2 GHz channel BW in the sub-terahertz and terahertz bands is the main envisioned approach for adding capacity. Given current peak spectral efficiencies of ~ 7 b/s/Hz per spatial layer, BW expansion could ideally provide 7 Gbps per 1 GHz. However, the transition to higher frequencies requires substantial fundamental research in hardware implementation and radio propagation modeling, and predicting real-world deployment timelines remains challenging. At present, real deployments are still mainly in well-studied FR1; in FR2, propagation mechanisms have been studied for a long time [11], and real deployments are starting to emerge in the lower part of FR2. Frequencies above 100 GHz are the focus of active research groups, but they are still in the very early stages of fundamental research [11, 12].

B. Single-user MIMO

Significant throughput gains in modern networks have been achieved through spatial multiplexing using MIMO. Current specifications support up to 8×8 MIMO in the DL and 4×4 in the UL for a single BS–UE link (single-user MIMO), but real-world deployments do not reach these ranks, mainly due to UE limitations: most support only 2×2 , or at best 4×4 , MIMO. In mobile devices, physical constraints restrict MIMO potential. The current baseline 2×2 MIMO implementation uses polarization diversity, meaning two cross-polarized antennas are co-located. Higher MIMO orders require spatial diversity, needing antenna spacing of over half a wavelength to provide sufficiently uncorrelated channels for spatial multiplexing — unfeasible at low frequencies (e.g., 15 cm at 1 GHz). As frequency rises, smaller antennas allow massive arrays in UEs for FR2. However, moving to FR2 does not enhance MIMO performance, as line-of-sight propagation dominates, making uncorrelated channels — and thus higher MIMO layers — unreachable. As a result, UEs in FR2 are generally expected to support at most two MIMO layers, provided by polarization, despite the total number of antennas likely being higher. Consequently, high-order spatial multiplexing can only be implemented in a limited frequency range, with the number of MIMO layers peaking around 3.5 GHz and rapidly decreasing to 2 layers below and above. This situation is reflected in current 3GPP specifications, which require UEs to support two antennas below 2.3 GHz (FR1), four above 2.3 GHz (FR1), and again two in FR2. There remains room for improvement in FR1. The 3.5 GHz band is currently a key driver of global 5G rollout. For example, in the popular n78 band (3300–3800 MHz), capacity can reach up to 28 Gbps (across 500 MHz) assuming 7 b/s/Hz spectral efficiency and 8 MIMO layers. Overall, there is

potential to enhance peak rates through MIMO, though these improvements are constrained. While FR1 offers potential for higher MIMO orders, it lacks the spectrum capacity, and higher frequency bands are unlikely to support configurations beyond 2×2 in UEs.

C. Multi-user MIMO and Beamforming

From a network-scale view, throughput is not limited by single-user MIMO. BSs can boost throughput through multi-user MIMO, where a BS with a high MIMO rank serves multiple UEs with lower MIMO capabilities simultaneously. For instance, a BS with 8×8 MIMO can serve four users with 2×2 MIMO each, using eight spatial layers in total. While the eight-layer limit applies to single-user MIMO, multi-user scenarios allow higher spatial resolution, with further improvements expected in 6G. Spectral efficiency gains are also anticipated from beamforming techniques. Massive antenna arrays enable BSs to form narrow, directional beams and dynamically generate multiple beams to serve users simultaneously, improving spatial reuse in dense areas.

D. Cell densification

An obvious ongoing trend for achieving higher throughput is cell densification. Dense BS deployment enhances spatial reuse, boosting capacity per unit area, but also worsens ICI. With current ISDs around 200 meters — and even 100–150 meters in real deployments — ICI is already a main capacity-limiting factor. In beyond-5G networks, as in 5G, a frequency reuse factor of one is expected for the macro layer. While this maximizes spectral efficiency in theory, it critically increases ICI in practice. In urban areas, macro-site ISDs are mainly driven by capacity needs rather than coverage, but closer site placement makes ICI management harder, setting a practical limit to macro-site densification. Micro-cell densification faces fewer ICI issues due to noise-limited planning (with antennas below rooftops and higher path loss at higher frequencies), though it remains much costlier than traditional networks. In any case, further densification will require advanced ICI cancellation techniques.

E. AI-driven optimisation

6G is announced to be AI-native across all network layers. From the air interface perspective, many tasks currently handled by conventional algorithms show promise for machine learning (ML) implementation. 3GPP working groups are investigating these possibilities, and we may see changes in future releases of 6G frame structures to support ML operations more efficiently, such as for tasks like channel estimation. While ML may not extend the theoretical throughput limits, it can help bridge the gap between theoretical and observed throughput by optimizing radio resource scheduling, beam selection, link adaptation, ICI mitigation, and other aspects.

F. Other assumptions

If there are no drastic changes with completely new technology in the 6G air interface and it remains OFDM-based, as in the fourth and fifth generations, we can assume that network capacity and spectral efficiency will increase through incremental improvements in the aspects discussed above. Improvements in modulation and channel coding techniques may offer limited theoretical gains. For instance, while modern hardware supports 4096-QAM (as in IEEE 802.11be Wi-Fi), it provides only a 20% increase in spectral efficiency compared to 1024-QAM (12 vs. 10 bits per symbol). Moreover, this gain is achievable only under ideal

conditions, with limited practical impact in typical deployments. Besides gradual improvements in the discussed aspects, there may also be qualitative leaps that are difficult to predict in advance. Some technologies that have long been studied could reach maturity and be incorporated into future releases. For example, full-duplex communication could theoretically double throughput by adding another multiplicative factor in the capacity formula (1). Similarly, concepts like Coordinated Multipoint transmission, which have existed since 4G but have not been implemented in real-world deployments due to synchronization challenges, may become viable with improved 6G transport link capabilities, enabling real-world implementation of cell-free/distributed MIMO architectures. Additionally, new capabilities introduced in 6G could unlock certain limitations. For instance, centimeter-level positioning accuracy, now emerging as a potential KPI for 6G, could significantly enhance radio resource scheduling algorithms.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a basis for throughput analysis in current-stage 5G networks and outlines some assumptions on the factors influencing the evolution of throughput-related KPIs in future network generations. Assuming no fundamentally new air-interface paradigm is introduced and 6G remains OFDM-based, the throughput evolution is most likely to be based on incremental improvements in the discussed factors, adding higher-level values to the reviewed formulas and/or by introducing new technologies that can be incorporated as new components into the calculations.

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